

COMBINING A REAL-TIME DOS ATTACK DETECTION WITH CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK

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Abstract— Denial-of-service (DoS) is a direct attack method that limits bandwidth and consumes resources on the server. DoS attacks are carried out by sending packets continuously from many different computers to the target server. For example, web servers of high-profile organizations such as banking, commerce and media companies, or government organization, etc.. For the above reason, to control and limit risks to server system resources, in this study, a DoS network attack model on the server has been proposed, and at the same time, a model has been proposed. DoS network attack detection is combined with a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model that has been trained on the NSL-KDD dataset previously, the dataset contains 125,972 different attack samples, training and testing results. The investigation accuracy is 99.331%, 99.186% respectively. After detecting the attack, the system is warned and an email is sent to the system administrator.

Keywords— Cybersecurity, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Denial-of-service (DoS), Deep Learning (DL), Hping3.

I. INTRODUCTION

Distributed denial of service (DDoS) is a challenge for cybersecurity experts, because it poses serious risks to servers. Developing an effective defense mechanism against these attacks is very important and challenging, the reason the attack types are so diverse and technically intensive. Various machine learning techniques have greatly aided in detecting DDoS attacks with low false positives and high detection rates. This survey [1] provides a comprehensive taxonomy of machine learning-based methods for detecting DDoS attacks, reviewing hybrid, unsupervised, and supervised approaches and analyzing the challenges involved. . This article aims to provide an in-depth understanding of DDoS attack detection mechanisms.

In this research article [2], An Analysis of Intrusion Detection Classification using Supervised Machine Learning Algorithms on NSL-KDD Dataset, Studying the behaviour of the supervised learning algorithms in detecting and classifying the abnormal traffic with very low false alarm rate. In this, both the binary and multi-class classification mechanisms have been studied using supervised classification algorithms such as Support Vector Machine (SVM), Naive Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbour (K-NN), Random Forest, Logistic Regression and Decision Tree using a well known benchmark network traffic NSL-KDD dataset with accuracy respectively 96.6977837%, 84.32717343%, 98.59655807%, 98.70451515%, 96.97085159, 95.83412714%.

In research [3] Internet of Things (IoT) network is the latest technology which is used to connect all the objects near us. Implementation of IoT technology is latest and growing day-by-day, it is coming with risk itself. So, it required the most efficient model to detect malicious activities as fast as possible and accurate. In this research paper, Deep Neural Network (DNN) is used to identify attacks in IoT. The performance of DNN in correctly identifying the attack was evaluated on the most used datasets, e.g., KDD-Cup'99, NSL-KDD, and UNSW-NB15. Experimental results show that the accuracy rate of the proposed method using DNN is over 90% for each data set and the accuracy rate of the NSL-KDD data set alone is 96.3%.

This paper [4] aims to build a network attack detection method suitable for the scale of large and high-traffic networks based on machine learning models using K-means, and DBSCAN clustering techniques. The detection technique is different from outlier detection commonly used in clustering-based anomaly detection applications. Experimental results on the NSL-KDD data set are positive with a detection accuracy of over 97.46%. And this paper presents [5] the implementation of an anomaly-based Intrusion Detection System (IDS), capable to detect well-known and zero-day attacks. The experiment used the Machine Learning (ML) model to evaluate the KDD99, NSL-KDD and CIC-IDS2018 datasets, in which the accuracy result for the RF algorithm was 93.998%.

Benedetto et al. [6] In this study, the ANIDINR (Anomaly-Based Network Intrusion Detection System) passive defense system is presented for the purpose of monitoring and protecting computer networks. The research direction is to minimize the undetected attack rate, false alarm rate and overall testing time and provide a step-by-step guide on selecting and implementing training methods for Machine Learning models (ML) and Deep Learning (DL). Using two datasets as input such as KDD Cup 1999 and NSL-KDD, five ML and DL models were evaluated for the accuracy of the dataset training process, in which the accuracy results of the SVM, RF, XGBoost algorithms are 93.80%, 97.93%, 97.67% respectively.

This article consists of 4 parts, the remaining parts are presented as follows: Part 2 is a presentation of the research object and method: CNN model, Training dataset, Evaluation method, DoS attack model, DoS attack detection model; part 3 is Experimental results and discussion; part 4 concludes this study.

II. RESEARCH OBJECTS AND METHODS

A. CNN model

Convolutional Neural Network has three main layers, including the convolutional layer, pooling layer, and fully connected (FC) layer.

Convolutional layer: The first layer is used to extract the various features from the input data. After extracting features, the convolutional layer outputs the result to the next layer.

Pooling layer: A pooling or downsampling layer reduces the dimensionality of the input using average pooling and max pooling functions.

FC layer: This layer is usually positioned before the output layer in a CNN architecture. The input data from the previous layers are flattened before passing into the FC layer. Consisting of the weights and biases, the FC layer is used to fully connect the neurons between two different layers.

```
model.add(Conv1D(32, 3, padding="same", input_shape = (X_train
model.add(MaxPool1D(pool_size=(4)))
model.add(Dropout(0.2))
model.add(Conv1D(32, 3, padding="same", activation='relu'))
model.add(MaxPool1D(pool_size=(4)))
model.add(Dropout(0.2))
model.add(MaxPool1D(pool_size=(4)))
model.add(Dropout(0.2))
model.add(Flatten())
model.add(Dense(units=50))
# output layer with softmax activation
model.add(Dense(units=5, activation='softmax'))
```

Fig. 1. Proposed CNN model

CNN has two parameters, the dropout layer and the activation function, as shown in Fig. 2.

Dropout: The features are connected to the FC layer. Dropout improves the performance of a machine learning model as it drops neurons from the neural networks during training.

Activation function: The activation function is the CNN model’s most important parameter. Here, the activation function uses the Softmax function, in fomular (1).

$$\sigma(z_i) = \frac{e^{z_i}}{\sum_{j=1}^K (e^{z_j})} \tag{1}$$

Here, Sigma (z_i) is the probability of the i^{th} word; K is the total length of the input vector and e^{z_i} and $\sum_{j=1}^K (e^{z_j})$ is the standard power function applied to each input value greater than 0, and the sum of the values between 0 and 1, respectively; z_i is the input vector value for the softmax function.

Dense is the model’s output layer evaluating results for five types of data: Normal, DoS, Probe, R2L, U2R.

B. Training dataset

The NSL-KDD dataset [7], [8] was published in 1999 in an international competition for knowledge extraction and data mining tools. The goal of the competition is to build a network intrusion detection system and a model to predict "malicious" connections called intrusions or attacks. The results of the competition were to collect a number of network traffic records and compile them into a dataset called KDD'99, and from there, the NSL-KDD dataset was created, as a revised version. conversion, optimization of KDD'99 from the University of New Brunswick.

The dataset includes 4 subsets: KDDTest+, KDDTest-21, KDDTrain+, KDDTrain+_20Percent, in which KDDTest-21 and KDDTrain+_20Percent are subsets of KDDTest+ and KDDTrain+. The KDDTrain+ dataset is used for training and KDDTest+ is tested. In the NSL-KDD data set, there are 4 types of attacks: Denial of Services (DoS), Probe, User to Root (U2R) and Remote to Local (R2L). described in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1. Table of attack attributes

Types	Attack attributes
DoS	apache2, back, land, neptune, mailbomb, pod, processtable, smurf, teardrop, udpstorm, worm
R2L	ftp_write, guess_passwd, httptunnel, imap, multihop, named, phf, sendmail, snmpgetattack, snmpguess, spy, warezclient, warezmaster, xlock, xsnoop
Probe	ipsweep, mscan, nmap, portsweep, saint, satan
U2R	buffer_overflow, loadmodule, perl, ps, rootkit, sqlattack, xterm

The data set consists of 43 attributes in each record, with 41 attributes related to the traffic itself, the last 2 being labels (attack or non-attack).

Table 2. Number of samples for each attack type in the NSL-KDD dataset

Types of attacks	Number of samples
Normal	67343
DoS	45927
Probe	11656
R2L	995
U2R	52

C. Evaluation method

In this study, we used evaluation methods such as a confusion matrix (CM) and Accuracy (Ac) to calculate the effectiveness of training data in machine learning algorithms, referenced from [9], [10] and [11].

The confusion matrix, as given by Equation (2), is used to evaluate the accuracy of the dataset. The confusion matrix contains the predicted and actual classifiers, which are empirically evaluated on a dataset.

$$CM = [TN \ FP \ FN \ TP] \tag{2}$$

- True positives (TP): correct malicious URLs predicted
- True negatives (TN): correct benign URLs predicted
- False positives (FP): incorrect malicious URLs predicted
- False negatives (FN): incorrect benign URLs predicted

Ac is the ratio of correct predictions to the total number of samples. Accuracy is defined by Equation (3).

$$Ac = \frac{TP+TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \tag{3}$$

D. DoS attack model

Building an attack model includes four computers: The hackers' computers have network addresses: 192.168.81.129, 192.168.81.130, 192.168.81.131, 192.168.81.132; The Server computer (victim) has network address 192.168.81.128 and the administrative computer used to monitor the remote server system has network address 192.168.81.127, as shown in Fig. 2. After building and installing the model, use Attackers to attack DoS on the target server computer using the Hping3 tool, followed by using the computer to remotely monitor the system, perform Capture packets and warn when there are unusual traffic problems on the server. Besides, the network diagram depicts Layer 2 Switch devices and ASA firewalls that serve as different functional management scopes: OUTSIDE, INSIDE, DMZ.

Fig. 2. DoS attack model to Server

The detection model described in Fig. 3, includes three main components: Server, Attacker, Monitor. The server is installed with a deep learning model and provides services to the system such as Web server, mail server, VPN, etc; Attacker is a machine that attacks DoS from the outside on the target machine and Monitor is a machine used to monitor servers and warn when there are system abnormalities.

E. DoS attack detection model

Fig. 3. DoS attack detection model

The steps are as follows:

Step 1: Server Computer

- Train the NSL-KDD dataset using a Deep Learning (CNN) model.
 - { Classification of labels: Nomal, DoS, Probe, U2R, L2R
 - Export model to file format
 - }
- Load the Deep Learning (CNN) model previously trained on the dataset.
- Use Wireshark tool: capture packets and analyze packets.

Step 2: The computer attacks

- Using Attacker machines to attack Server computers (Web, mail, etc.)
- Tools for attack such as Hping3

Step 3: Server Computer

- Use Wireshark tool: capture packets and analyze packets, read packet data
- Feed the data into the trained CNN model to compare attack identification
- Compare the IP address in the packet with the server's IP address and determine the type of attack label
 - { If ((target_ip) > 100 and (check { labels: "Dos, Probe, U2R, L2R" }))
 - Notification {Attack}
 - Else {" nomal"}}

Step 4: Monitor Computer

- If an unusual problem occurs in the Server system, the monitoring machine will receive a warning Notification to system administrator email.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experiments are evaluated using a server with a hardware configuration such as two CPUs 2.30GHz E5 2696 v3 (36 cores, 72 threads), RAM 64Gb DDR4, NVIDIA® GeForce RTX™ 3060 GPU 12Gb.

1) Experimental results

a) Training results of deep learning model

In the process of using the CNN model to train the NSL-KDD dataset, the split ratio between the data used for training and testing is 80% and 20%, respectively. That is, the total number of data samples is 125,973, of which 100,778 data samples are used for training and 25,195 data samples are used for testing. The results after training are that the accuracy rates of training and testing data are 99.331%, 99.186%, respectively, in Figure 4 and Figure 5.

```

train_results = model.evaluate(X_train, y_train, verbose=1)
print(f'Train results - Loss: {train_results[0]} - Accuracy: {train_results[1]}')

3150/3150 [=====] - 9s 3ms/step - loss: 0.0246 - accuracy: 99.33120608329773%
Train results - Loss: 0.024573124945163727 - Accuracy: 99.33120608329773%

# predicting target attribute on testing dataset
test_results = model.evaluate(X_test, y_test, verbose=1)
print(f'Test results - Loss: {test_results[0]} - Accuracy: {test_results[1]}')

788/788 [=====] - 2s 3ms/step - loss: 0.0324 - accuracy: 99.1863489151001%
Test results - Loss: 0.03241690248250961 - Accuracy: 99.1863489151001%
    
```

Fig. 4. Accuracy results of training and testing data.

The loss function in Fig. 6, according to the data chart of Train and Test, the closer it is to 0, the higher the accuracy of the data training model.

Fig. 5. Accuracy results of train and test data with Epochs = 100.

Fig. 6. Loss function results of train and test data with Epochs = 100.

b) Experimental results of detecting DoS attacks

In this DoS attack detection model, the scientific research team has built and tested a practical application model to serve as a foundation for further research. The memory resources allocated to the attacking machines are RAM (4Gb), CPU (1 core) at 2.30GHz and the server is RAM (8Gb), CPU (2 cores) at 2.30GHz.

2179699	24.043618	192.168.81.129	192.168.81.128	TCP	60	30438	→ 0	[<None>]	Seq=3752902996	Win=512	Len=0
2179700	24.043619	192.168.81.130	192.168.81.128	TCP	60	10099	→ 0	[<None>]	Seq=3541269965	Win=512	Len=0
2179701	24.043654	192.168.81.132	192.168.81.128	TCP	60	61970	→ 0	[<None>]	Seq=836249649	Win=512	Len=0
2179702	24.043655	192.168.81.131	192.168.81.128	TCP	60	65508	→ 0	[<None>]	Seq=3437524248	Win=512	Len=0

Fig. 7. Result of packet capture and attack detection

Figure 7, On the server, Wireshark software is used to capture online packets, then check the packets and detect IP addresses 192.168.81.129, 192.168.81.130, 192.168.81.131, 192.168.81.132, sending packets continuously to The Server has address 192.168.81.128. Immediately, the monitoring machine warns of a DoS attack as shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. DoS attack warning from Server

In Figure 9, the DoS attack has been identified and alerted to the administrator's Email: ptithcmnckh@gmail.com in the network security monitoring system.

Fig. 9. DoS attack warning to system administrator's email

In Figure 10, the Central Processing Unit (CPU) resource occupied is 3% at normal time, meaning the server has not been attacked by DoS, corresponding to Figure 11, the CPU resource occupied is about 70% at the time of operation. DoS attack, because this type of attack will continuously send HPING3 packets to the Server to request continuous processing, so CPU resources increase, meaning the CPU will be occupied with a large amount of resources, after a period of time. Otherwise, the server will stop working until the server is restarted by the system administrator.

Processes						
Name	Status	CPU	Memory	Disk	Network	P
Task Manager		3.3%	18.8 MB	0 MB/s	0 Mbps	
Windows Explorer		0%	25.7 MB	0 MB/s	0 Mbps	

Fig. 10. CPU resources are used at normal times

Processes						
Name	Status	CPU	Memory	Disk	Network	F
System		61.5%	0.1 MB	0.1 MB/s	0 Mbps	
System interrupts		7.6%	0 MB	0 MB/s	0 Mbps	

Fig. 11. CPU resources are occupied at the time of DoS attack

2) Discussion and evaluation of the results

During the experiment, the CNN deep learning model was used to evaluate the NSL-KDD data set, the distribution of the data ratio used for training and testing was 80% and 20%, respectively, meaning 100,778 data samples are used for the training process and 25,195 data samples are used for the testing process with a total number of data samples of 125,973 data samples. After training, the accuracy of the trained data and tested data is 99.331%, 99.186% respectively.

From the results of the model, the data set was trained, used as a network attack detection model. Experimental results showed that the DoS attack sent packets to the Server to request continuous processing. At this time, the Server processed requests continuously, and consumed 61.5% of CPU memory resources, after Then the Server will be overloaded. After the system detects a DoS attack, the attack warning is notified and sent via email to the network security monitoring system.

Through surveying the results of related research projects using the same NSL-KDD data set, the training results achieved the accuracy described in Table 3. According to the statistical results table, the accuracy of The research team is more effective.

Bảng 3. Comparison table of research results using the NSL-KDD data set

Author et al.	ML and DL algorithms	Accuracy (%)
[2]	Support Vector Machine	96.6977837%,
	Naive Bayes,	84.32717343%,
	K-Nearest Neighbour	98.59655807%,
	Random Forest,	98.70451515%,
	Logistic Regression	96.97085159%,
	Decision Tree	95.83412714%
[3]	Deep Neural Network	96.3%
[4]	K-means	97.46%
[6]	SVM,	93.80%,
	RF,	97.93%,
	XGBoost	97.67%
Proposed model	CNN	99.331%

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In the study, the CNN deep learning model was used to train the NSL-KDD dataset, which has been published and has been used by many cybersecurity experts to evaluate, proving that The reliability of the dataset used is very effective. In the study, two problems were raised: training the NSL-KDD dataset with the DL model and building a DoS network attack model in the internal network.

Experimental results evaluate the accuracy of the deep learning model for training data and test data as 99.331%, 99.186% respectively. From the results of the trained CNN model, used to detect input data for the DoS attack detection model, the experimental results have identified the type of DoS network attack, and at the same time warned and sent email to network security monitoring system administrator.

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